

PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF MOS₂ NANOSHEETS AND MOS₂ NANOSHEETS/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Report the preparation of MoS₂ nanosheets suspensions based on liquid exfoliation method. The suspensions are characterized by absorbance and photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy. The results show the PL signal from suspensions is enhanced evidently. Meanwhile, obtain the optimized process conditions which are increasing of ultrasonic time, decreasing of centrifugal rotational speed, using large-size bulk MoS₂ and adding ball-milling process. The PL main peak of single MoS₂ nanosheet is located at 652 nm, which corresponds to a band gap of 1.9 eV. Besides, the single MoS₂ nanosheet is annealed. Because mild annealing could make the lattice distortion in MoS₂ nanosheet which appeared in exfoliation reversed and the semiconducting property of the as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheet is largely restored, the PL signal from single MoS₂ nanosheet is enhanced after annealing. SEM and AFM show the most MoS₂ nanosheets have a lateral size of several hundred nanometers and a thickness of several nanometers. Besides, prepare MoS₂ nanosheets reinforced epoxy composites by mixing MoS₂ nanosheets suspension and E51 epoxy. The PL signal from composites is enhanced as well. That means the MoS₂ nanosheets dispersing in epoxy still keep enhanced PL signal and E51 epoxy could not influence the band gap properties of MoS₂ nanosheets. The composites are annealed. And compared with the composites which are not annealed, the PL signal from annealing composites shows obvious shift which could be ascribed to residual thermal stress in the composites. Meanwhile, the toughness of the composites is also improved, and it is because of the excellent toughness of MoS₂ nanosheets and the dispersion strengthening in the composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Two-dimensional (2D) nanosheets are a kind of thinnest functional materials and they possess a thickness of molecule or atom[1, 2]. Graphene are the most familiar 2D nanosheets. Besides, some semiconductor 2D nanosheets such as BN, MoS₂, TiO₂ and et.al are also essential functional materials[3, 4]. MoS₂ is an important transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs)[5, 6]. And it is S-Mo-S sandwich structure in layer, adjacent sheets stack via van der Waals. Monolayer MoS₂ nanosheets, which are produced by bulk MoS₂, a kind of indirect band gap materials, are turned into direct band gap materials. MoS₂ nanosheets exhibit an increase in photoluminescence. This phenomenon makes MoS₂ nanosheets appear specific reaction to light, electric, magnet and heat and have tremendous application potential in semiconductor industry[7-9]. It is demonstrated by theory and experiment that the band gap width of MoS₂ nanosheets varies as strain changing[10-14]. Besides, MoS₂ nanosheets owe excellent mechanical property[15, 16], which also makes them have great potential in reinforcing composites and flexible electronic devices.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Based on the Liquid Exfoliation studied by Coleman etc[17], we choose different technological parameters to produce MoS₂ nanosheets suspension. Firstly, mix the commercial bulk MoS₂ with

disperse solvent (NMP, DMSO, NVP) and the initial MoS₂ concentration was 100 mg/ml. Sonicate the mixtures in water bath at power output of 200W for 1h or 6h. The resultant dispersions were centrifuged at 1500 r/min, 3000 r/min or 6000 r/min for 45mins and the supernatants were collected. To improve the exfoliation, we referred to some previous literatures[18-21] and decided to choose ball-milling before sonicate to optimize process. The rotate speed and time of ball-milling were 25rpm and 40min respectively. Figure 1 shows the MoS₂ nanosheets suspensions which are prepared by dispersing solvent NMP, NVP and DMSO.

Figure 1: Photos of MoS₂ nanosheets suspensions which are prepared by dispersing solvent NMP, NVP and DMSO

The MoS₂ nanosheets/epoxy composites were prepared by blending method. Mix the MoS₂ nanosheets suspensions prepared by NMP and E51 epoxy. Stir and sonicate the mixture to enhance the dispersion of MoS₂ nanosheets in epoxy. Heat the mixtures to make NMP boil away. After adding curing agent, the mixtures were formed under normal temperature for 24h. Figure 2 is as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheets reinforced epoxy composites.

Figure 2: (a) Photos of MoS₂ nanosheets reinforced epoxy composites tensile samples, (b) Photos of MoS₂ nanosheets reinforced epoxy composites film

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The MoS₂ nanosheets suspensions prepared by NMP are orange, and they are closed to the suspensions in previous literatures. It can be concluded that NMP is better disperse solvent. Besides, the MoS₂ nanosheets suspensions prepared by NMP were characterized using Absorbance and PL spectroscopy. The Abs and PL of suspensions are more intense, the concentration of MoS₂ nanosheets in suspensions is higher, and the thickness of MoS₂ nanosheets is thinner.

Figure 3 (a) shows the Abs data of 1-1#, 2-1#, 3-1# MoS₂ nanosheets suspensions. The sonicate times suspensions are 1h, 1h and 6h, and the centrifugal rotational speeds are 1500 rpm, 3000 rpm and 1500 rpm respectively. By comparing the Abs of different suspensions, it is concluded that increasing of sonicate time and decreasing of centrifugal rotational speed could make the Abs of MoS₂ nanosheets suspensions enhanced. In figure 3 (b), the 5-1-1# suspension was prepared by adding ball-milling process and the Abs of 5-1-1# suspension is higher. Besides, using large-size bulk MoS₂ could also enhance the Abs of MoS₂ nanosheets suspensions.

Figure 3: (a) Absorbance of MoS₂ nanosheets suspensions prepared by different ultrasonic time or centrifugal rotational speed, (b) Absorbance of usual MoS₂ suspension and MoS₂ suspension prepared by adding ball-milling process

Figure 4 shows the PL spectrums of as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheets suspension, pure NMP and bulk MoS₂. The PL signal from MoS₂ nanosheets suspension is enhanced evidently. It means that there are a large number of MoS₂ nanosheets in the suspension and the MoS₂ nanosheets approach monolayer.

Figure 4: Photoluminescence(PL) spectrums of MoS₂ nanosheets suspension, pure NMP and bulk MoS₂

Using micro-area PL testing, the PL signal from single MoS₂ nanosheet was obtained. Figure 5 (a) are the PL spectrums of single MoS₂ nanosheet, bulk MoS₂ and quartz plate. Compared with bulk MoS₂, single MoS₂ nanosheet also exhibits an obvious increase in PL and the main peak is at 652 nm, which corresponds to a band gap of 1.9 eV. This result is consistent with theoretical analysis and previous literatures. It can make sure that the as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheets approach monolayer, and the band gap properties and band gap width of them have changed. The single MoS₂ nanosheet is annealed at 230 °C in vacuum. Figure 5 (b) are the PL spectrums of pristine single MoS₂ nanosheet and annealed single MoS₂ nanosheet. After annealing, the PL signal from MoS₂ nanosheet is enhanced. This result owes that mild annealing could make the lattice distortion in MoS₂ nanosheet which

appeared in exfoliation reversed and the semiconducting property of the as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheet is largely restored.

Figure 5: (a) Photoluminescence(PL) spectrum of single MoS₂ nanosheet, bulk MoS₂ and quartz plate, (b) Photoluminescence(PL) spectrum of pristine single MoS₂ nanosheet and annealed single MoS₂ nanosheet

The SEM and AFM images of as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheets are shown in figure 6. The analysis of SEM and AFM indicates there are many distinct differences between MoS₂ nanosheets and bulk MoS₂. The plane size of most MoS₂ nanosheets is about 100nm~300nm, and the thickness is about 6 nm, approaching 5 layers. The MoS₂ nanosheets prepared based on Liquid Exfoliation in previous literatures are 8 ~ 15 nm thick. Compared with them, the as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheets are thinner.

Figure 6: (a) SEM images of as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheets, (b) AFM image of as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheets

Figure 7 shows the PL spectrums of as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheets/epoxy composites(a) and E51 epoxy(b). Owing to the MoS₂ nanosheets, the composites exhibit enhanced PL signal as well. And the main PL peak is also obvious. That means the MoS₂ nanosheets dispersing in epoxy still keep enhanced PL signal. E51 epoxy could not influence the band gap properties of MoS₂ nanosheets. And there is very good compatibility between MoS₂ nanosheets and E51 epoxy matrix.

Figure 7: Photoluminescence(PL) spectrum of MoS₂ nanosheets reinforced epoxy composites and E51 epoxy

The MoS₂ nanosheets/epoxy composites were annealed at 140 °C in vacuum for 1h. After annealing, the composites were cooled in the air. Because the composites were film, the cooling rate was rapid. The PL spectrum of as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheets/epoxy composites and annealed MoS₂ nanosheets/epoxy composites were obtained. Figure 8 (a) shows the PL spectrums of these two kinds of composites. Compared with the composites which were not annealed, the intensity PL signal from annealed composites exhibits a modest increase. Meanwhile, the PL peak is sharper. In addition, the PL peak position of annealed MoS₂ nanosheets/epoxy composites appears obvious blue shifted, and the shift is about 6.6 nm. This phenomenon could be ascribed to the residual thermal stress in the composites. MoS₂ nanosheets and epoxy possess different thermal expansion coefficients. If MoS₂ nanosheets and epoxy were unconstrained, they would occur different deformation after cooling. However, when MoS₂ nanosheets and epoxy formed composites, they restricted each other by interface. By interface effect, MoS₂ nanosheets were stressed by epoxy(Figure 8 (b)). The band gap width of MoS₂ nanosheets varied as strain changing and the PL main peak of MoS₂ nanosheets shifted. Most MoS₂ nanosheets in the composites were wrapped by epoxy. That leads the PL signal from composites shift as well. Utilizing this phenomenon, by testing PL signal shift from MoS₂ nanosheets/epoxy composites, the residual thermal stresses in the composites could be measured. And this is a new kind of non-contact measurement method.

Figure 8: (a) Photoluminescence(PL) spectrum of usual and annealed MoS₂ nanosheets reinforced epoxy composites (b) Schematic of MoS₂ nanosheet stressed by residual thermal stresses from epoxy

The tensile mechanical properties of MoS₂ nanosheets/epoxy composites were also tested. Figure 9 shows the stress-strain curves of different composites. No.1 composites were prepared by 40% epoxy and 60% as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheets suspension. No.2 composites were prepared by 67% epoxy and 33% MoS₂ nanosheets suspension. And No.3 composites were prepared by 17% epoxy and 83% MoS₂ nanosheets suspension. Besides, some mechanical properties parameters of MoS₂ nanosheets/epoxy composites were shown in table 1. Compared with pure epoxy, with the increase of MoS₂ nanosheets concentration, the Young modulus of composites decreases slightly. Nevertheless, the maximum strain exhibit obvious increase. As can be seen from stress-strain curves, epoxy was brittle fractured but obvious plastic deformation occurs in the composites before fracturing. It indicates the toughness of MoS₂ nanosheets/epoxy composites improved. It could be attributed to the excellent toughness of MoS₂ nanosheets. Moreover, the concentration of MoS₂ nanosheets is about 0.01% and the lateral size of most nanosheets is about several nanometers. That means MoS₂ nanosheets have a function of dispersion strengthening in the composites. In dispersion strengthening, second phase could not be loaded but it could prevent cracks. It also makes the toughness of MoS₂ nanosheets/epoxy composites improved.

Figure 9: Stress-strain curves of different MoS₂ nanosheets reinforced epoxy composites

sample	Young modulus (GPa)	Maximum strength (GPa)	Maximum strain (%)
epoxy	3.056	79.323	3.346
1	2.647	53.141	10.196
2	2.970	63.682	4.295
3	2.312	55.915	13.484

Table 1. Tensile properties of different MoS₂ nanosheets reinforced epoxy composites

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we have prepared MoS₂ nanosheets suspensions and MoS₂ nanosheets reinforced epoxy composites. The results show the PL signal from as-prepared MoS₂ suspensions is enhanced evidently. Meanwhile, we obtain the optimized the process conditions which are increasing of ultrasonic time, decreasing of centrifugal rotational speed, using large-size bulk MoS₂ and adding ball-milling process. Because mild annealing could make the lattice distortion in MoS₂ nanosheet which appeared in exfoliation reversed and the semiconducting property of the as-prepared MoS₂ nanosheet is largely restored, PL signal from annealed MoS₂ nanosheet is enhanced as well. By analyzing the results from the as-prepared composites, it is demonstrated that MoS₂ nanosheets dispersing in epoxy still keep enhanced PL signal and E51 epoxy could not influence the band gap properties of MoS₂ nanosheets. And compared with the composites which are not annealed, the PL signal from annealing composites shows obvious shift which could be ascribed to residual thermal stress in the composites. Meanwhile, the toughness of the composites is also improved, and it is because of the excellent toughness of MoS₂ nanosheets and the dispersion strengthening in the composites.

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